

RDA P14 JOINT SESSION - Helsinki, 25 oct 2019
SHARC / FAIRsharing / FAIR Data Maturity Model groups

The challenging FAIRisation route: how could assessment help?

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Introduction, Anne Cambon-Thomsen

3 RDA groups (SHARC IG, FAIR Data Maturity Model WG, FAIRSharing Registry: connecting data policies, standards & databases WG) having overlapping objectives, but different methods and routes to FAIR have joined for a collective discussion throughout this session.

The 1st part showed the contribution of the different groups while in the 2nd part, the audience have provided contribution by discussing in different sub-groups.

Part 1. Presentations + quick interactions 65 min

RDA-SHARC ig: towards recommendations / guidance -

Laurence Mabile, RDA-SHARC ig

The group aims to unpack and improve crediting and rewarding mechanisms in the data/resources sharing process. Specifically:

Work out a list of criteria to assess FAIRness to prepare FAIRisation of data (see FAIR data maturity model wg) and of community (training, planning, governance, evaluation...); Review the existing rewarding mechanisms in various scientific communities, assess their limits, and identify key factors to improve (ex: tools, incentives, requirements...); Encourage the integration of data sharing-related criteria including FAIRness criteria in the global scientific activity evaluation scheme at the European and national institutional levels; and plan processes for stepwise adoption of principles necessary for implementation measures tuned to national, local and institutional contexts. Some guidance is needed to enable credit /reward, to various stakeholders and is needed to plan, train and build FAIRness literacy for an increased sharing capacity.

Some communities and projects (INRA, EC-IMI FAIRplus, Belmont forum PARSEC communities) will help implementing and adjust such recommendations.

CHALLENGING PROCESSES that need to be planned early in the FAIRification route (pre-fairification steps, see next sections...)

FAIR criteria assessment survey main comments on preFAIRification-

Romain David, RDA-SHARC ig

In each community, it is needed to assess FAIRness before automatization: stakeholders need to understand FAIRisation and particularly what they have to do and why. Implementation requires means for each action and training for different kinds of stakeholders.

FAIRness assessment tools are to be realistic and usable in a short time, and adaptable for each stakeholder from survey's feedback). Implementation requires stepwise processes with a first step reachable by all community members. For a better understanding, organising steps is crucial to empower all stakeholders through iterative and participative processes

SHARC has worked on a list of criteria (that has to be understandable). FDMM WG is working on establishing a machine actionable set of criteria but we need for gradual integration.

SHARC group proposed 5 steps (adaption to stakeholders is desirable)

i) Fostering pre-FAIRification decision ii) Planning pre-FAIRification training iii) Structuring pre-FAIRification processes iv) Ensuring all criteria are well understood v) Enabling crediting and reward. All these steps must be adaptable to the kind of data regarding the available

resources and must take into account community FAIRness literacy. This includes the definition of the level of compliance for quality aspects (rich metadata, curation?) and how to involve wisely means and time of researchers to obtain i) Minimum requirement ii) optimal actions for a real improvement of FAIRness.

Further detail in the poster: Lessons from a tool of FAIR literacy based on key assessment criteria 10.5281/zenodo.3539270 <https://zenodo.org/record/3539270#.Xcq8eehKiUk>

How can the FAIR criteria best be employed in guiding the researcher in the pre-FAIRification stage?

Edit Herczog, RDA-FAIR Data Maturity Model group

EH co-chairs the wg; she is a former politician trained to consensus building. There are also people in the WG who know a lot about data.

Research data has to be FAIR. What does this mean? How can you measure it? Can RDA make single criteria to check FAIRness? One criteria might be too hard to achieve. You need incentives for researchers to speed up the development.

FAIR principles were used as measurement (each word as 1 measure) and in addition more criteria were developed by researchers (~100) - Those were combined, now about 50 criteria.

You have to get metadata, rich metadata. What is RICH metadata? What is sufficient metadata? This is one major obstacle. What is a knowledge representation?

We need to optimize FAIR principles to FAIR 2.0 principles.

Are we interested just in FAIR, or in the interconnection of F+A, I+R, etc.?

We need to weight the criteria. Not all are similar important. You can see criteria on RDA homepage. Mandatory, recommended or optional criteria. Does it work for each domain? We do not believe. We have to figure out the footprint of the community. Can we use the same measurement for all domains? We think so. Also different schools use the same measurements. How do you get to the FAIR footprint? Criteria will be tested in a workshop.

Who can use the criteria? Can be used first and most for self-assessment. Then you choose if you need a methodologist for your domain.

We would like to get it into the HORIZON Europe program. It is important so that institutions will value it.

Questions from audience:

ORCID will be added to evaluation. What is the privacy issue? (This is actually a question for Pete)

- ORCIDs are not involved in Edits project. We develop a tool and anyone can use. Pete: In the FAIR Evaluator, your ORCID is currently required in order to generate an evaluation but is not visible to people browsing collections, and so should not be a problem for privacy. It is required so the FAIR Evaluator knows who you are so you can find your assessments later on (and to be

able to contact for questions as it is in an early stage of development). ATM it is a pilot/prototype.

- If you're FAIR your in and if you're not you might be out in terms of funding...is this where we are heading?

If you are a policy maker, you want data to be shared. But there is no answer that can be used for all. We cannot set the bar too high - everyone would lose motivation. If you set the bar too low - there is no improvement at all. It is a stepwise process. Researchers have to learn that it is not only important to have data Findable, at some point you have to focus also on Interoperability for example.

FAIRsharing and the FAIR evaluator - how to assess the right standards, and the right repository for your data -

Peter McQuilton, UK

Metadata standards and identifiers are of 4 types:

- Data models and formats
- Controlled vocabularies, thesauri, ontologies
- Unambiguous, persistent identifier schemata
- Minimum information reporting requirements, checklists

Capture information about all 4 types → split into ~40 metadata fields; capture also community standards. Vast majority are ontologies. Linking to repositories, which will link the standards for the data (one step in FAIRisation of data).

Policies by journals, funders say that you should (i) use community standards and (ii) store data in repositories. You need advice and people which help you to choose the right solution for you. FAIRsharing.org aims to guide consumers and help producers to make resources more visible and more widely adopted. All info in FAIRSharing is manually curated. FAIRsharing works with a lot of people: GOFAIR, RDA, journals (to improve journal data policies).

Assessing FAIRness: is an aspirational target (you come always closer) and reflects the extent to which a digital resource addresses FAIR principles. The FAIR Evaluator: designed as bottom-up community effort, building on 'generation 1' FAIR Metrics (human entry) to create 'generation 2' FAIR maturity indicators that use FAIRsharing metadata <http://w3id.org/AmlFAIR>. It is community-driven: community can decide which maturity indicators are relevant to them, they're registered in the evaluator (with documentation), anyone can execute an evaluation on any GUID, extremely open.

FAIRsharing enables FAIR principles: ensures that standards, databases, repositories are FAIR

Questions from audience:

Is software also involved? Is achieving FAIRness the goal?

- Software is tricky to be FAIR; FAIRsharing does not include software/code. ELIXIR group is working on a position paper on software/code. It is a slightly different use case to that of FAIRsharing.
- If you look after your data appropriately, they will be FAIR. It is a continuum - we always have to improve and go further.

The user can add indicators according to community. If a user does not know the indicators, is there a solution to use the tool?

- There is a set of metrics as a default which can be used by the user. You can see what other people are doing. So a user can test how FAIR he is, by checking with other users. We need training for that. The tool comes with the default set - working group finalizes the output. Training will need to be provided in collaboration with each community.

Potential of FAIR principles as tools in creating Open Science assessment frameworks: two examples -

Heidi Laine, University of Helsinki, FI

FAIR is not the same as open. But the open science policy discussion has also opened up the discussion about FAIR. FAIR is compliant with open science principles.

Two examples of incentives for Open Science (researcher and institutional level):

Finish open science maturity assessment:

- Conducted by Finnish ministry 2015, 2016 (institutions), 2017 (funding institutions), 2019 and ongoing
- Monitor progress made by open science and research initiative
- Data gathered by survey and collecting from external websites
- Did not focus on the content of data policy, but which organizations do already have a policy.
- Became part of the ministry's portfolio of tools
- University of Helsinki was 'winner' 2016, may change in 2019
- Universities should strive to be at level 5

The criteria of assessment (with subcriteria): Strategic steering; Policies and principles; Supporting openness; Competence development

Knowledge Exchange Open Scholarship:

- Research infra and service development
- Partners: DFG, JISC; CNRS etc.
- Help researchers to make open science/open scholarship related activities more visible, somewhere along the road to provide this as a tool for actors who evaluate researchers.
- Potential open science merits based on various outputs: software, DMPs, research data, research articles, teaching, conference talks; and on skills: coding, DM-related skills.

Questions from audience:

Peer-review is usually very closed. There are a few approaches to make it open, but how do you see it as open-metric?

- It is part of the researchers work. Work that they did has to be validated.

Once you get the badge or recognition for open science? How long does it last?

- Openness profile concept is dynamic. It will be added according to your activities. You'll just be able to show more and more attitude. Data stewards/curators etc. will also have contributions.

Can we stop using "coding" as a skill? Coding has a different meaning in social science (interpreting qualitative data). It is better to use "software development"

Is there a reference to the new criteria?

Part 2- Interactive discussion 25 min

We suggested an active participation of audience as part of 3 discussion groups corresponding to the 3 questions (Q1 to Q3, see below).

- **Discussion summary**

Q1 : What is the place of FAIR assessment as regards other elements of scientific activities involved in data sharing?

Data sharing involves different scientific activities including FAIR assessment. It is not entirely clear whether or not criteria of FAIR assessment can be considered as part of quality data assessment or only data management quality assessment. However, the researcher's role is to choose an appropriate repository which provide the utmost FAIR services, e.g. metadata longevity, where metadata is kept even if underlying research data is deleted.

Scientific disciplines have very diverse types of research data which, in turn, leads to different requirements. It would be desirable to FAIRify everything, however it is not realistic given e.g. historical data in non digital records. Nevertheless, all data should be made as FAIR as possible. In addition, making data open, citable and trustworthy are also crucial parts of data sharing.

In order to enhance treatment of data according to FAIR principles, organisations should be assessed based on how well they support their researchers to be FAIR. This could become part of the scientific evaluation process by e.g. funders checking deposit of data. In any case, findability is the first step to be tackled.

Q2 : How can the FAIR criteria best be employed in guiding the researcher in the pre-FAIRification stage?

In order to guide researchers to the pre-FAIRification stage different stakeholders have to be involved: funders, policy makers at national level and publishers (to make FAIR data a requirement), institutions (to provide infrastructure, training, support and policies at their departments e.g. in the library) and disciplinary communities (to create community standards). This illustrates that researchers have to be supported throughout the entire life cycle of research data starting from generation until final publication and archival.

The FAIRification process involves a cultural change. Until now, many institutions do not validate FAIR principles when evaluating researchers, however, this is an essential aspect for reproducibility of research. In addition, researchers should be supported by data management professionals embedded in institutions. Also institutional libraries provide a central point where repositories are managed and coordinators are embedded. FAIR principles need to be adequately rewarded and training needs to be provided. This can be mediated via shaped RDM policies, where those points are considered (e.g. University of Helsinki).

Q3 : What is the role of repositories and standards providers (assessment for evaluation)? How can they ensure that their resources are visible and used by the community to enable FAIR data? How can FAIRsharing help?

Common naming convention for classifying standards for reporting and sharing (meta)data or other objects would be favourable, assuming that those standards are registered and therefore reusable and mappable. Standards such as RDF, OWL and SKOS help to improve machine-readability of metadata.

In order to increase visibility of repositories to researchers and policy makers, they have to outreach in the community via targeted education, publicity at events and reporting success stories. In addition, repositories can register in [repositoryfinder.datacite.org](https://www.datacite.org/repositoryfinder) or [Re3data.org](https://re3data.org) and CoreTrustSeal (CTS) certification increases visibility.

By checking metadata surrounding the research data it can be measured whether standards are used. This can be done by OAI-PMH which provides an application-independent interoperability framework based on metadata harvesting. In addition, the FREYA project visualization tool for persistent identifiers (PIDs) helps to check whether standards for metadata were used. Hereby, PIDs can provide unambiguous linking between PIDs of the same type, e.g. journal articles citing other journal articles, or of different types, e.g. linking a researcher and the datasets they produced.

- **Minutes of the sub-groups' discussion**

The objective of this part 2 is that each participant (who will identify himself as part of 1 of the 3 groups) will be invited to argue for or against at least one assertion/question in the present google doc or on paper.

- **Q1** : What is the place of FAIR assessment as regards other elements of scientific activities involved in data sharing? **Chair: Anne**

Specifically:

- **Q1.1**: some criteria of FAIR assessment can be considered as a part of quality of data assessment, give some examples / some not, give some examples
- **Q1.2**: All data should not be FAIRified / Give some examples
- **Q1.3**: FAIR assessment criteria should be part of the scientific evaluation process (grant applications, call for projects, individual scientist evaluation of activities, recruitment and career steps, teams or laboratories evaluation, institution policies' assessment, other?) / Give some examples of criteria that could be used

Comments from participants:

- **Q1.1:**

-FAIR assessment is important but we believe it does not say much about data quality. Quality of the data and quality of data management are two different things.

-Measuring FAIRness of data can help improve quality and can make researchers think about managing their data well. Disciplinary repositories can play an important role in curating and ensuring the quality of the datasets they host.

-FAIR can not assess the quality but quality of data (and metadata) is important to be FAIR (eg. reusability potential of data) (Janet Stebe)

-Quality of data is not included in the FAIR principles; it is important but not part of FAIR (Mark Dekkers)

-Quality is not measured by FAIR principles (Nick Juty)

-Interoperability: researcher must define his concepts (Mohamed Yahia)

-All the FAIR principles can be regarded as data quality assessment. The FAIR metrics project's aim is to map the principles to measurement processes. However, some metrics are about the data repository. In those cases the researcher's role is to choose the 'best' repository which provides more FAIR services, eg. A2's metric is 'Metadata longevity' so the repository should guarantee that the metadata keep exists even after the removal of the data. The researcher usually does not have a direct impact on the repository's policy about deletion. This metric is measuring the data through. <http://fairmetrics.org> (Peter Király)

- **Q1.2:**

-Not all data need to be made available, thus not all data need to be FAIRified. It might not be worth spending time and effort on this. As a minimum, data behind publications should be made available and you should make the data FAIR as much as possible.

-It might be useful though in making available data that might not be important for your own research but could be useful for other researchers (who work in different disciplines).

- In some disciplines it might be extremely important to share 'not important' results (e.g. negative) - for instance in clinical research.
- All data should not be fully fairified, ex: sensitive data such as geolocalisation of endangered species or of some sensitive installation (Mohamed Yahia)
- While it would be great to fairify everything, it is probably not realistic, especially given historic data in non digital records...
- First, what needs to be made available, hierarchy of data? Those in publications, data highly already reused..
- Data that is already highly reusable and already very widely reused. FAIRification in the sense of evaluation; the formal indicators would be a waste of resources (Mark Dekkers)
- It is not all about FAIR and it is not just about FAIR. Open, Citable, Trustworthy are also important. We shouldn't see FAIR as a finite findable? State ut should be moving along the continuum of FAIRness and unlocking FAIR potential over time (Fiona Murphy)
- I disagree. FAIR is not a binary state. All data should be made as FAIR as possible/reasonable. What is possible and/or reasonable is for the disciplinary community to define (Heidi Laine)

- **Q1.3:**

- Data deposition in repositories might be the first step for evaluation. Funders can check whether data is deposited, whether it has a doi and is findable. Findability is the first step (realistically-speaking).
- Maybe it depends; it is a useful rubric but no model is perfect; we shouldn't wish to try to reshape existing frameworks critical reflection (Fiona Murphy)
- Depends on interpretation and definition of FAIR scientific excellence; should remain the primary criteria. Organisations should be assessed based on how well they support their researchers to be FAIR. (Heidi Laine)
- Agree where applicable (Nick Juty)
- Yes, all. Value to have evolving target.
- Reusability: because it is the aim of FAIR data (Mohamed Yahia)
- **Q2** : How can the FAIR criteria best be employed in guiding the researcher in the pre-FAIRification stage?

Possible chairs: Edit and Heidi

Specifically:

- **Q2.1:** Which stakeholders need to be involved to prepare researchers for making their data FAIR ? Which aspect of FAIR will each stakeholder cover? (open question)
- **Q2.2:** How can researchers best be prepared in the pre-FAIRification stage for making their data FAIR? (open question); Is this a once off or will there be aspects that will need to be revisited throughout the research lifecycle?

Comments from participants:

- **Q2.1:**

- Funders: make FAIR requirement
- Data publishers/repositories: make FAIR requirement

- Data producers:
- Institutions: Policies (must have the services, support, etc. to support policies), technical infrastructure, central funding and support, informing, training, license guidance, reward and incentive plans
- Libraries: point of training, point of people physically managing institutional repos, coordinators, interpreting funder requirements; libraries are regarded as service provider, but they should have strategic priority for the institution.
- Data management professionals, dispersed throughout institutions in a variety of models. (see RDA group on data architecture)
- Research policy makers at the national level. Must place emphasis on FAIRness and craft incentives. They could contribute to criteria. Perhaps an interaction with DMPs.
- Disciplinary communities: Standards for metadata, expectations for data completeness and what is included in acceptable datasets.
- University of Helsinki is updating the data policy. If the university requires FAIR principles, on the other side there is also training and FAIR principles are seen as a merit. Need to be adequately rewarded.
- Many institutions do not measure open science when they evaluate the researchers.
- We try to get cultural change. We have to go vertically and horizontally.
- Help of funders for dissemination in any shape is valuable. -
- Sophie Aubin:

1/ National & institutional level

Policy creation (what to do)

Funding (means to do it)

General guidelines (how to do it)

2/Support services like information professionals, IT people

Training / informing

Providing services so that FAIR is transparent to data/code/producers

3/Evaluation responsables

Include FAIR practises in evaluation

Rewards (carrier)

Tina Kakela:

-universities & other research organisations

-funders (national, european, other)

-Governments via budget and legislation

-Publishers

-Research life cycle until publication

-institutional policy in communities; incentive to inform?

-institution policy : necessary services / labs; understanding & benefits; all shape research policies

-Funders / public sector stakeholders that shape national research policy to give incentives

- Research Lifecycle until publication

- "Culture and name changing"

institutional policy in INRA -> communities
incentive to inform?

-institution policy

-> necessary services and tools

-> understanding and the benefits

Shape the research policies

"lising" more from services to strategic stakeholders

information offer

- **Q2.2:**

- Responsibility for interoperability: Developers. Researchers.
- Responsibility for reusability: Institutions

- **Q3:** What is the role of repositories and standards providers (assessment for evaluation)? How can they ensure that their resources are visible and used by the community to enable FAIR data? How can FAIRsharing help?

Chair: Pete

- **Q3.1:** There is no agreed naming convention for classifying standards for reporting and sharing data, metadata and other digital objects. Do you think we need such common classification?
- **Q3.2:** How can a repository increase its visibility to researchers and policymakers?
- **Q3.3:** To measure the use and adoption of standards, showing which repositories implement them is essential, but how else can the adoption of standards be measured?

Comments from participants:

- **Q3.1:**

-3 YES + BenS: Yes, a common naming conventions would be good (provided that it registered as an DO itself so it is reusable and mappable).

-We should have a once only policy for metadata. Which gives flexibility for choosing the metadata you feel is appropriate for you. Through RDF OWL & SKOS this can have either structured relationships to other terms or fuzzy connections to other terms. When a structured axiom can't be defined or agreed then SKOS can be used. When humans/machines look for metadata then the richness is dependent on how much is provided and we can put the emphasis on the search agent knowing what to look for. Put the pressure on searcher on away from the researcher (provider). For data exchange between registries there is an ISO which could be applied for being included in EOSC Common Catalogs: Registry Interchange Format - Collections and Services (RIF-CS) (ISO 2146). It is implemented by the Australian Research Data Commons: <https://vocabs.ands.org.au/viewById/1>

- **Q3.2:**

-relate to FAIR- Matrix FIP (FAIR IMPLEMENTATION PROFILES) for repositories (Barbara Magagna)

-Community engagement

-For Policy makers : Certification (e.g. CTS)

-Ensure it is included in registries - e.g. re3data (which is being used in developing tools for DMPs)

Community outreach - targeted education, publicity at community events, success stories

BenS: Activate the relevant community (on various levels of scales) and stimulate scientific debate on the use of standards.

-impl science.org; CoreTrust Seal (Tom Smede?)

-Kristan Garza: Register in RepositoryFinder.org or in Re3data.org; Add embedded metadata in schema.org in their pages for Google Dataset Search to find them

-1) OK if it visible in DMP

2) schema.org

3) link the repository + standards + communities (GOFAIR Matrix)

4) CTS (Core Trust Seal)

- **Q3.3:**

-Through the dataset's metadata

-BenS: Through metadata

- Tom Smede?: FREYA project visualization of link quality; "harvard" schema OAI-PHMY

...

Comments welcome at:

<https://docs.google.com/document/d/1c4m2G-FhjjNZKZdCMIqkyhMqeyRmYeQuiZSz-EYhXZU/edit?usp=sharing>